

SMART AUTOMATIC PARKING SYSTEM USING NODEMCU MICROCONTROLLER

¹Gaibnazarov B.B, ²Makhmudov M.A, ³Tuychiev F.F, ⁴Abduraimov O. T

^{1,2,3,4}Tashkent State Technical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11207694>

Abstract. This article presents the design and implementation of a smart automatic parking system using the NodeMCU microcontroller. The system utilizes four ultrasonic sensors, one servo motor, and an LCD display to create a prototype parking system that improves the efficiency and safety of parking processes. The system aims to automate parking procedures and provide real-time feedback on parking space availability.

Keywords: NodeMCU, LCD display, parking, microcontroller, automation.

INTRODUCTION

Parking management has been a long-standing challenge in urban areas, leading to inefficiencies and delays for drivers. The introduction of smart parking systems has the potential to revolutionize parking management by optimizing the process and providing real-time information.[1] In this paper, we present a smart automatic parking system prototype that uses the NodeMCU microcontroller to achieve these objectives.

Materials and Methods

NodeMCU Microcontroller

The NodeMCU microcontroller serves as the central processing unit for the parking system. It receives input from sensors and controls other system components.

Ultrasonic Sensors

Four ultrasonic sensors are positioned around the parking area to detect the distance and position of vehicles. These sensors provide the necessary data to guide the parking process.

Servo Motor

A servo motor is used to control a barrier gate, which allows vehicles to enter and exit the parking area.

LCD Display

An LCD display is employed to show real-time information such as parking space availability and system status.[2] This provides visual feedback to drivers and enhances their parking experience.

System Design and Implementation

The smart automatic parking system operates as follows:

Vehicle Detection: As a vehicle approaches the parking area, the ultrasonic sensors detect its distance and position, providing data to the microcontroller.

Parking Space Availability: The system assesses available parking spaces based on sensor data. If a parking spot is available, the servo motor-controlled barrier gate opens to allow the vehicle entry.[3]

Vehicle Guidance: The system uses sensor feedback to guide the vehicle into the available parking space safely.

Display Information: The LCD display provides drivers with real-time information on parking space availability and system status.[4]

Vehicle Exit: When the driver is ready to leave, the system verifies the vehicle's position and opens the barrier gate to allow the vehicle to exit.

Pic. 1. Electrical diagram of system

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The prototype smart parking system demonstrates improved efficiency and safety in parking management. The real-time data provided by the sensors enables the system to optimize parking space utilization and minimize the risk of collisions.

The use of the LCD display enhances the driver experience by providing clear and concise information on parking availability. Additionally, the system's automation reduces human error and the potential for traffic congestion.[5]

CONCLUSION

The smart automatic parking system using the NodeMCU microcontroller offers a promising approach to modernizing parking management.[6] By automating the process and providing real-time feedback, the system can improve efficiency, safety, and the overall parking experience. Further research and development could lead to more advanced and scalable solutions for parking management in urban areas.

REFERENCES

1. "Arduino Programming in 24 Hours, Sams Teach Yourself" - Richard Blum.
2. "Exploring Arduino: Tools and Techniques for Engineering Wizardry" - Jeremy Blum.
3. "Arduino Cookbook" - Michael Margolis.
4. "Getting Started with Arduino" - Massimo Banzi.
5. "Programming Arduino: Getting Started with Sketches" - Simon Monk.
6. "Make: Electronics: Learning Through Discovery" - Charles Platt.